

Assessment of Demonstration Method on Performance in History Teaching and Learning activities among Secondary School Teachers' in Kwara State, Nigeria

Alabi, Jimoh Adeniyi¹

alabi.aj@unilorin.edu.ng

+2348137455721

Oniye, Masud Ibrahim¹

oniyemasud@unilorin.edu.ng

+2348033850768

&

Ijaiya, Badirudeen Adebayo¹

ijaiyabadirudeena@gmail.com

+2348067252981

¹Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

Teaching requires a teacher to nurture his/her knowledge and skills constantly to prepare for the lessons, use appropriate teaching method such as demonstration to illustrate, analyses and critique issues specifically in History subject. Hence, this study investigated the assessment of demonstration method on performance in History teaching and learning among secondary school teachers in Kwara State. Descriptive research type was used and the population comprised all senior secondary school History teachers during the 2024/2025 academic session. Incidental sampling technique was used to select 180 History teachers from 364 senior secondary schools in Kwara as respondents for this study. A questionnaire was used to collect data from respondents. The instrument was validated by two experts in the Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education University of Ilorin, Nigeria. A test-retest reliability method was used and a coefficient index value of 0.67 was obtained as reliability. Mean ranking, independent t-test and One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyse the data. The findings showed that use of demonstration method makes History teaching and learning stimulating, stress-free, practical and appealing to the students. Moreover, there was a significant difference in the use of demonstration method in teaching History based on teachers' gender, qualification and teaching experience. The study concluded that male teachers used demonstration method efficiently in teaching History than females in senior secondary schools. It was recommended that government should recruit more qualified History teachers to teach History in secondary schools to support effective use of demonstration method in teaching History.

Keywords: Demonstration method, History Teaching and Learning

Introduction

Teaching is an interactive process that takes place between teacher and the students in a classroom aimed at changing the behaviour potential of the students in right direction. It is a cooperative activity between teacher and students in which teacher involve students in different classroom activities, such as organisation, management, discussion, recitation and evaluation of results for the realisation of a specified set of instructional objectives. According to Agwu (2022), teaching is an interaction between teacher and students under the teacher's duty to bring about the expected change in students' behaviour. It is the process that requires a teacher to cultivate his/her knowledge and skills continuously to prepare for the lessons and use appropriate teaching method for the effective delivery of the instructions in the class.

Saidu and Jekayinfa (2020) stated that teacher needs to plan properly for the lesson because it is through planning that the teacher can determine the scope and sequence of units, topics as well as teaching methods to be used in the lesson. Thus, teaching History in the classroom involves illustrations, analyses and critique of issues which require teachers to plan properly for the lesson and apply appropriate teaching methods such as demonstration method that suit specific goals and purposes to make History teaching and learning a life-changing and rewarding experience for the students. Therefore, to determine the level of knowledge that students will achieve in History class, demonstration method is needed to create conducive learning environment, stimulate learning motivation, support student active learning and facilitate good interaction between learners and the teacher (Widodo, 2016). Furthermore, it is believed that effective teaching and learning of History cannot take place, if an appropriate and stimulating

method such as demonstration is not used to teach students in the classroom (Fadeiye, 2010). Hence, teachers need to use pedagogical strategies that can facilitate the desired learning outcomes. Most of these active learning methods require the greater participation of the students in comparison to the traditional teaching approaches known as teacher-centred method.

However, to surmount the challenges encountered in classroom interactions, the demonstration method is needed by the teacher to facilitate effective teaching and learning. Adewale and Effiong (2015) asserted that demonstration method is a strategy that involves visual presentation of the action and activities or practical work related to the facts and principles of a delivered lesson by the teacher in the classroom aiming to facilitate the task of teaching and learning. In this method, the teachers dramatise topics to be taught while students put it to practice the skills demonstrated to show their level of efficacy in the performance of those skills. This means that demonstration method is a technique of teaching in which the new subject matter is delivered and used by the teacher before it is imitated by the students in the classroom. Ajayi (2015) explained that demonstration method helps the students to have a clear picture and comprehensive knowledge on a subject matter that they did not understand before and thereby performed better, most especially in History subject. It is believed that a good demonstration method is always accompanied by explanation which is typically a discussion. There is no way the teacher will demonstrate the lesson without explaining it. So, the demonstration usually effective in teaching a skill that can be observed because it helps students to have better understanding on the subject matter, gaining more knowledge on political, cultural and socio-economic issues nationally and internationally (Afolabi, 2018).

Moreover, Adewale and Effiong (2015) further stated that demonstration method requires teachers to plan all the activities relating to demonstration in great detail and ensure that all the equipment, illustrations and other relevant materials are procured in time and kept ready before the demonstration begins, breakdown the demonstration into suitable steps so that it can be easily understood by the students and proceed with the demonstration slowly to enable all the students grasp it in details. Therefore, to facilitate effective teaching and learning in History subject, demonstration method is essential to provide an in-depth knowledge, understanding of an issue and stimulate further interest in the subject. The New Secondary School History Curriculum (2017) stipulated that History is a subject that exposes students to the body of knowledge that will enable them to appreciate it as an instrument of national integration and nation building. It is a subject that emphasis the drama of human beings or the stage of the world which is still growing on, and this drama should be dramatised and presented before students in a perfect manner in the classroom. Therefore, History teacher, male or female needs to be qualified, experienced and proactive to teach the subject in a way that will arouse students' interest through the use of demonstration method.

Conversely, Akiri and Ugborugbo (2008) noted in their study titled "An examination of gender's influence on teachers' productivity in secondary schools" that male teacher' behaviours towards the use of teaching methods in teaching students are better than female teacher in secondary schools. In addition, Roghaiyeh and Praveena (2013) argued that male teachers are usually more productive by using methods of teaching than their female counterparts in secondary schools. In the same vein, Yakubu (2023) observed that teacher' academic qualifications and teaching experience are very important for positive academic achievement of students. This indicates that teacher's academic qualification and experience bringing a noticeable difference in the quality of students produced and that teacher-student relationship, teachers' academic qualification and experience are of great contributions to achievement of students in secondary schools. Also, the professional qualifications a person acquires and practices over the years equip him or her with experience on the job (Mugoya, Muleke & Mwangi, 2022). Also, Irvine (2019) revealed that years of teaching experience used by teachers predict and relate to teachers' effectiveness in classroom activities. However, Yusufu, Luka, Daniadi and Gotul (2019) explained that in some secondary schools, History subject is handled by unqualified and less experience teachers rather than qualified and experienced teachers who will teach History and motivate the students to perform better in their academic performance.

Since the returned of History to secondary school curriculum in 2019 as a separate subject History teaching in secondary schools has continued to dwindling over the years. This may be as a result of unqualified and less experienced History teachers who adopted inadequate teaching and instructional methods to teach History in the class which makes some students to lose interest in understanding the concepts of History and thereby affect their academic performance in the subject. Afolabi (2018) conducted a study on the prospects and challenges of teaching and learning of History in Oyo State, Nigeria and discovered that few secondary schools in Oyo State were offering History as a subject due to the inconsistent government policy towards the subject, inadequate number of qualified and experienced History teachers, insufficient instructional materials and lack of History textbooks are the problems of teaching and learning History subject in secondary schools.

Objectives of the Study

This study investigates the:

1. Teachers' use of demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State.

2. Use of demonstration method by male and female teachers in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State.
3. Demonstration method used by qualified and unqualified teachers in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State.
4. Whether there is significant different in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on years of teaching experience.

Research Questions

1. How do teachers' used demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State?
2. Is there any significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher's gender?
3. Is there any significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on qualified and unqualified teachers?
4. Is there any significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on years of teaching experience?

Research Hypotheses

- Ho1:** There is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher's gender.
- Ho2:** There is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher qualification.
- Ho3:** There is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on years of teaching experience.

Methodology

Descriptive research type was adopted in this study. The population of the study comprised of all secondary school teachers in Kwara State, while the target population was senior secondary school History teachers in Kwara State. Incidental sampling technique was used to select 180 History teachers from all the 364 secondary schools in the state as respondents for this study. This is because History teachers are not many in schools and they were sample as they were come across. A researcher's designed questionnaire was used to collect data and was divided into two sections (A and B). Section A contained demographic information of the respondents on gender, qualification and years of teaching experience, while section B contained items on the use of demonstration methods with four Likert scale type and graded as 4= Strongly agree (SA). 3= Agree (A). 2= Disagree (D) and 1= Strongly disagree (SD). The validity of instrument was established after the series of corrections by the two experts in the field of History Education and Test and Measurement. A test-retest reliability method was used and a coefficient index value of 0.67 was obtained as reliability. The instrument was used to collect data from the respondents by the researcher and six research assistants. The data were analysed using Mean rating, independent t-test and One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 significance levels.

Result

The percentage was used to describe Demographic Data of the respondents. Research question 1 was answered using mean rating and any item with a mean greater than 2.50 was considered as agreement with stated research question and vice-versa. Research questions 2, 3 and 4 had corresponding hypotheses and were tested. Hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested using t-test statistic while hypothesis 3 was tested using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Table 1 shows the demographic data of the respondents.

Table 1

Demographic Data of the Respondents Gender, Qualification and Teaching Experience		
Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	105	55.0
Female	75	45.0
Total	180	100
Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
NCE	25	13.9
B.A	15	8.20
B.A Ed	95	54.5
M.A plus PGDE	18	9.00
M.A	8	4.90
M. Ed	19	9.50
Total	180	100
Qualified teachers	132	74.5
Unqualified teachers	48	25.5
Total	180	100
Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 5 years	50	28.5
6 – 15 years	100	55.5
16 years and above	30	16.0
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 1 revealed that majority of the respondents was male 105 (55.0%) while females were 75 which are (45.0%). This shows that male teachers were more than female teachers in the respondents. Also, 132 (74.5%) of the teachers sampled were qualified while 48 (25.5%) were not qualified. 50 (28.5%) were less experienced teachers. 100 (55.5%) were experienced teachers and 30 (16.0%) were more experienced teachers.

Research Question 1: How do teachers' used demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State?

Table 2: Teachers' Use of Demonstration Method in Teaching History among Secondary School Students in Kwara State

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	X
1	Each time, I usually use demonstration method to teach History in the class.	88 (61.5%)	48 (24.2%)	25 (7.7%)	19 (6.6%)	3.51
2	My students understand more better when I use demonstration method to teach them.	75 (57.7%)	50 (25.4%)	23 (6.9%)	32 (10%)	2.50
3	I select demonstration method to teach students' because it makes my work easier, practical and appealing to the students.	65 (48.5%)	61 (33.7%)	20 (6.8%)	34 (11.2%)	3.65
4	Some students did not even comprehend when I use demonstration method to teach.	63 (47.7%)	45 (22.3%)	41 (19.5%)	31 (10.5%)	2.40
5	I prefer demonstration method with explanations than any other method.	73 (57.1%)	51 (25.5%)	33 (10.5%)	23 (6.9%)	3.42
6	I normally have an interactive class with my students when I used demonstration method.	72 (55.5%)	59 (29.2%)	30 (8.7%)	19 (6.6%)	3.55
7	The students understand topics such as Nigerian civil war, military rule in Nigeria and other topics involving practical and dramatisation if I use demonstration method to teach them.	60 (46.5%)	56 (32.5%)	28 (7.8%)	36 (13.2%)	3.60
8	The method helps me to make visual presentation of fact and principles of the subject matter in the classroom.	75 (57.1%)	50 (25.5%)	32 (10.5%)	23 (6.9%)	3.63
9	Demonstration method enables me to facilitates good interaction with my students and use to determine the level of knowledge that students have achieve	60 (46.0%)	58 (32.0%)	24 (7.8%)	38 (14.2%)	3.42

10	I use demonstration method to presents clear picture and comprehensive knowledge of the subject matter for my students so that they can understand better.	48 (24.2%)	80 (59.5%)	25 (7.7%)	27 (8.6%)	3.50
Grand Mean						3.32

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 showed the teachers' use of demonstration method in teaching History. It is clear from the findings that a majority of the respondents agreed that students understand better when demonstration method is used to teach them in the classroom because it shows the clear picture and comprehensive knowledge of the subject matter to the students as well as makes their work stimulating, stress-free, practical and appealing to the students. A majority of the respondents were of the opinion that demonstration method facilitates good interaction between teachers and learners; it is used to determine the level of knowledge that students have achieved and as well, prefer to use demonstration method for teaching History than any other method. Therefore, the grand mean score of 3.32 which was greater than the benchmark of 2.50 showed that the use of demonstration method has a strong influence on the teaching and learning of History. This means that an-effective use of demonstration method makes teaching and learning History more appealing to the teachers and students' interest.

Ho1: *There is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on gender.*

Table 3: Use of Demonstration Method of Teaching History among Secondary School students in Kwara State Based on Teacher's Gender

Gender	No	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Remark
Male	105	14.920	2.344	178	2.210	0.001	Ho ₁ Rejected
Female	75	12.310	2.401				

*Significant $p < .05$

Table 3 showed the t-value of 2.210 and calculated p-value of 0.001 for 178 degrees of freedom computed at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, since the calculated p-value of 0.001 is less than critical value of 0.05, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students based on teacher's gender is rejected. This indicates that there was a significant difference in the use of demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher's gender.

Ho2: *There is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher qualification.*

Table 4: Use of Demonstration Method of Teaching History among Secondary School Students in Kwara State Based on Teacher's Qualification

Qualification	No	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Remark
Qualified	132	18.120	2.334	178	2.612	0.002	Ho ₂ Rejected
Nonqualified	48	10.112	2.405				

*Significant $p < .05$

Table 4 showed the t-value of 2.612 and the calculated p-value of 0.002 for 178 degrees of freedom computed at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, since the calculated p-value of 0.002 is less than critical value of 0.05, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students based on teacher qualification is rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in the use of demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher qualification.

Ho3: *There is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on years of teaching experience*

Table 5: Use of Demonstration Method of Teaching History among Secondary School Students in Kwara State Based on Teacher's Years of Teaching Experience

Sources of variation	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F-value	Sig	Remark
Between group	263.871	2	11.740	50.62	0.000	Ho ₃ Rejected
Within group	1142.037	177	10.245			
Total	1405.907	179				

***Significant $p < .05$**

Table 5 indicated that the f-value of 50.62 and the calculated p-value of 0.000 computed at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, since the calculated p-value 0.000 is less than the critical value of 0.05, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the use of demonstration method of teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher years of teaching experience is rejected. This shows that there was significance difference in the use of demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher years of teaching experience.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study revealed that the use of demonstration method shows the clear picture and comprehensive knowledge of the History to the students as well as makes teachers' work stimulating, stress-free, practical and appealing to the students. A majority of the History teachers were of the opinion that demonstration method facilitates good interaction between teachers and learners and students understand the concepts in History subject better when demonstration method is used to teach them.

The outcome of the finding showed that there was a significant difference in the use of demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher's gender. This implies that male History teachers used demonstration method in teaching History than their female counterparts and they are more experienced in handled the subject with the use of demonstration method in teaching History students than female teachers. This finding supports the finding of Roghaiyeh and Praveena (2013) that male teachers are usually more productive in using methods of teaching than their female counterparts in senior secondary schools. The result of the finding indicated that there was a significant difference in the use of demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher qualification. This revealed that qualified History teachers used demonstration method in teaching History in senior secondary schools than non-qualified teachers. This finding is in line with the finding of Yusufu, Luka, Daniadi and Gotul (2019) that in some secondary schools, History subject is handled by unqualified and less experience teachers rather than qualified and experienced teachers who will teach History and motivate the students to perform better in their academic performance.

Moreover, the finding of the study showed that there was significance difference in the use of demonstration method in teaching History among secondary school students in Kwara State based on teacher years of teaching experience. This indicated that very experienced and experienced teachers used demonstration method in teaching History and very experienced teachers used the method appropriately and wisely in teaching History among senior secondary school students in Kwara State. This finding corroborates the finding of Yakubu (2023) that teacher' academic qualifications and teaching experience are very important for positive academic achievement of students and they bring a noticeable difference in the quality of students produced in secondary schools. In addition, Irvine (2019) revealed that years of teaching experience used by teachers predict teachers' effectiveness in classroom.

Conclusions

The study concluded that the use of demonstration method shows the clear picture and comprehensive knowledge of History to the students and makes teachers' work stimulating, stress-free, practical, and appealing to the students, facilitates good interaction between teachers and students and makes students understand the concepts in History subject better. Also, male teachers are more experienced in handled History subject with the use of demonstration method in teaching students than female teachers. Similarly, qualified History teachers used demonstration method than non-qualified History teachers in teaching History among senior secondary school students in Kwara State, and that demonstration method is used effectively by very experienced and experienced teachers in teaching History among senior secondary school students in the State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommended are made:

- i. Teachers should be encouraged by the government and school authorities to use demonstration method properly to teach History subject so that it can help students to develop critical thinking.
- ii. There is the need for government to recruit more qualified History teachers to teach History subject in secondary schools to enable effective teaching and learning of the History.
- iii. There should be regular supervision of teachers on the appropriate use of demonstration method for teaching History subject in secondary schools.

- iv. Schools' management should provide teachers with adequate teaching resources to guarantee effective use of demonstration method and give room for students' participation in order make learning meaningful to the students.

Acknowledgements

Our profound gratitude goes to all our senior colleagues who are experts in the field of History Education, Educational Measurement and Evaluation at the Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, the researcher's assistants, school management and the History teachers' who have helped in one way and the other to effect corrections on the instrument, data collection, and all those who provided enabling environment for administration of questionnaire and who also took their time to respond to the questionnaire for the success of this study. God bless you all.

References

- Adewale, S.A. & Effiog, O. (2015). Effect of two methods on student's achievement in junior secondary schools in Yakurr, Cross River State; *International Letter of Social and Humanistic Sciences*, 1(61): 70 – 81.
- Afolabi, O. O. (2018). Education development in Africa: Prospects and Challenges of Teaching/Learning History in Nigeria. *Frontiers in Education Technology*, 1(1): 1 – 23.
- Agwu, S. N. (2022). Curriculum delivery band security challenges in Nigeria. *Journal of Curriculum Organisation of Nigeria (CON)*, 29(3): 1 – 5.
- Ajayi, A. O. (2015). Towards effective teaching and learning of history in Nigerian secondary school. *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJRSSH)*, 2(2): 137 - 142.
- Akiri, A. A. & Ugborugbo, N. M. (2008). An examination of gender's influence on teachers' productivity in secondary schools. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 17(3): 18 – 27.
- Fadeiye, J. O. (2010). Groundwork essay on history and historiography: Archaeology and Methods of Teaching History, Ibadan, Murfat Publication.
- Mugoya, P., Muleke, P. & Mwangi, A. (2022). Impact of teachers' qualification on secondary school history teaching and learning in Kajara County, South-western Uganda. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 3(3): 77 – 90.
- New Senior Secondary School Curriculum (SSSC) History (2017). *Nigerian educational research and development council (NERDC)*. Yaba: NERDC Printing press.
- Roghaiyeh, S. S. & Praveena, K. B. (2013). Influence of gender and type of school on job performance among school teachers. *Indian Streams Research Journal*, 3(8): 30 - 38.
- Saidu, A. & Jekayinfa, O. J. (2020). How to teach and test History. In R. A. Lawal (Eds.). *Teaching Methodology in the Humanities*. Ilorin: Niyi Printing & Publishing Co.
- Sengai, W. & Mokhele, M. L. (2021). Teachers' perceptions on development and implementation of History 2167 syllabus in Zimbabwe. *Cypriot Journal of Educational science*, 16(3): 916 – 927.
- Widodo, H. P. (2016). Developing an informed curriculum for initial teacher education: Building Student Teachers' Theoretical and Practical Knowledge and Shaping Teacher Identity. *Reflective Practice: International Journal and Multidisciplinary Perspective*, 1(1): 69 – 79.
- Yakubu, S. (2023). Teacher academic qualification as a correlate of students' academic achievement in Fine and Applied Arts at the Colleges of Education in Northern Nigeria; *International Journal of Innovative education research*, 11(1): 15 – 22.
- Yusufu, S. Y., Luka, M. L., Daniadi, B. J. & Gotul, G. G. (2019). History teachers' qualification, experience and level of implementation of the senior secondary school History curriculum in Plateau State. *Journal of the Nigerian Academy of Education*, 18(2): 83 – 94.